

Exploring miR-10a/b Expression in Leukemia Cell Lines: Implications for Biomarker Discovery in Acute Leukemias

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Abstract

Introduction:

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are short noncoding RNAs that play crucial regulatory roles in various cellular processes. Among them, miR-10a and miR-10b (miR-10a/b) have been widely studied in cancer research due to their established association with multiple malignancies. Several studies have reported dysregulated expression of these miRNAs in different types of cancer, including hematologic malignancies. However, their specific role in acute myeloid leukemia (AML) and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) remains to be fully elucidated. In this study, we aimed to investigate the expression changes of miR-10a/b in HL-60 and MOLT-4 cell lines, representing AML and ALL, respectively, and compare their expression levels with those in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs).

Methods:

To identify relevant miRNAs, a multistep filtering approach using various databases was employed. Specific primers complementary to stem-loop structured miRNAs were designed for precise quantification. RNA was extracted from cultured HL-60 and MOLT-4 cells as well as PBMCs, followed by expression analysis using reverse transcription quantitative PCR (RT-qPCR). The relative expression levels of miR-10a/b were determined and compared across different cell types.

Results:

The data analysis revealed an upregulation of miR-10a/b expression in both HL-60 and MOLT-4 cell lines compared to PBMCs. These findings suggest a potential role for miR-10a/b in leukemia progression.

Discussion:

The observed increase in miR-10a/b expression in AML and ALL cell lines aligns with previous reports linking these miRNAs to malignancies. The upregulation of miR-10a/b may contribute to leukemia pathogenesis by influencing key regulatory pathways. Further investigation is needed to explore the functional implications of these miRNAs in leukemic transformation, disease progression, and response to therapy.

Conclusions:

The elevated expression of miR-10a/b in HL-60 and MOLT-4 cells suggests that these miRNAs may serve as potential biomarkers for AML and ALL. Future studies should validate these findings in patient samples and explore their utility as prognostic or diagnostic markers in leukemia.

Keywords: miR-10a, miR10b, microRNA, acute myeloid leukemia, acute lymphoblastic leukemia, cancer.

1. Introduction

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a major class of cytoplasmic non-coding RNAs consisting of 19-22 nucleotides with a single-stranded stem-loop structure. These molecules modulate gene expression at the post-transcriptional level, usually by specifically binding to complementary sequences at the 3' untranslated region (UTR) of relevant messenger RNAs (mRNAs) (1). Aberrant expression of miRNAs, either in

improper tissues or with significant changes in their levels, has been associated with various disorders, including cancers. Investigating their expression profiles—simultaneously measuring the expression levels of miRNAs—has established their role in tumorigenesis, either by upregulating oncogenes or downregulating tumor suppressors (2).

The miR-10 family consists of two members: miR-10a and miR-10b (miR-10a/b). Previous studies have demonstrated an association between abnormal expressions of miR-10a/b and an increased risk of developing various human cancers; however, the results are not conclusive (3-7). Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) are malignancies of hematopoietic stem cells and are among the most common types of leukemia worldwide. AML primarily affects adults over 45 years old, while ALL is largely diagnosed in children between the ages of 1 and 4 (8, 9). Therefore, developing new strategies to better confront these malignancies is necessary, and recent advances suggest that early diagnosis and therapeutic measures will be significantly beneficial (10).

In this study, we implemented a dual approach to elucidate the upregulation of miR-10a/b in leukemia cell lines. First, we evaluated the expression profiles of miR-10a/b in HL-60 and MOLT-4 cell lines, which are representative of AML and ALL, respectively, in comparison to peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) to confirm results reported from other studies. Second, we utilized various databases to perform bioinformatics analyses, aiming to identify functionally related genes and pinpoint the most relevant miRNAs targeting key genes within these pathways.

2. Materials and Methods

PBMCs isolation, Cell lines and Cell culture

Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated from a healthy donor without any diagnosed disease. Twelve milliliters of whole peripheral blood were collected in an EDTA-K2-anticoagulated vacuum tube. The blood sample was then transferred to a tube containing 30 ml of heparin and centrifuged at 1800 rpm for 8 minutes. After removing the plasma, the precipitated cells were diluted with 15 ml of RPMI medium. In a new tube, 10 ml of this solution was gently layered over 5 ml of Ficoll-Hypaque1 (Innotrain, Germany) and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 20 minutes. PBMCs were collected from the interface between the lower Ficoll and the upper RPMI solution.

The HL-60 cell line (ATCC Number: CCL-240, link) and the MOLT-4 cell line (ATCC Number: CRL-1582, link) were obtained from the Pasteur Institute of Iran. HL-60 cells were cultured in IMDM medium (Iscove's Modified Dulbecco's Medium, Thermo Fisher, USA) supplemented with 20% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco, USA). The MOLT-4 cell line was cultured in RPMI 1640 medium containing GlutaMAX™ Supplement and HEPES (Thermo Fisher, USA), enriched with 10% FBS.

In brief, 1 cc of the cell suspension along with 2 cc of the respective media was transferred to a sterile 25 cm² culture flask containing 100 IU/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin

(Gibco, USA). Each cell line was cultured in triplicate and incubated at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere with humidity for 6 days. The culture media were changed every two to three days to maintain optimal conditions. PBMCs were cultured in RPMI medium enriched with 10% FBS and incubated under the same conditions for 2 days.

RNA Extraction, cDNA Synthesis, and Reverse Transcription-Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-qPCR)

Total RNA was extracted from 400 µL of cell culture suspensions utilizing the Beta Prep Total RNA Isolation kit (Beta Bayern, Germany) following the manufacturer's protocol. One milliliter of cold RNX-Plus was added to the buffy coat and thoroughly mixed by pipetting. The suspension was then transferred to a 1.5 mL microtube and vortexed for 1 minute.

After a 5-minute incubation at room temperature, 200 µL of chloroform was added, and the mixture was vigorously shaken for 1 minute. Following a 5-minute incubation at 4°C, the mixture was centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 20 minutes. The aqueous phase was then transferred to a new microtube, mixed with an equal volume of cold 100% ethanol, and incubated overnight at -20°C.

Subsequently, the solution was centrifuged at 1200 rpm for 45 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was washed with 1 mL of cold 70% ethanol. After a 15-minute centrifugation at 1200 rpm at 4°C, the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was air-dried. The RNA pellet was resuspended in 30-50 µL of RNase-DNase free water, and the RNA concentration was determined. The RNA samples were then stored at -70°C.

For cDNA synthesis, 1 µg of total RNA from each sample was reverse transcribed using the AddScript cDNA Synthesis Kit (AddBio Inc., South Korea). The RNA was mixed with 1 µL of random hexamer primer and diluted to 10 µL with DEPC-treated sterile water. The mixture was incubated at 65°C for 5 minutes, followed by cooling on ice, the addition of 10 µL of RT-premix, and gentle mixing. The reaction was then incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes, followed by 50°C for 1 hour, and terminated at 70°C for 10 minutes. The quality and quantity of RNA and cDNA were measured using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (BNMS-N100 Micro spectrophotometer, China).

RT-qPCR was performed with 1 µL of cDNA (600 ng/µL concentration) using miR-10a/b specific primers on a Step One Plus real-time PCR system (Applied Biosystems, CA, USA). GAPDH (RefSeq: NM_002046.7) served as the reference gene for normalization. Relative expression levels were calculated using the Δ Ct and $\Delta\Delta$ Ct methods. Expression data were analyzed and visualized using GraphPad Prism (Tables 1).

Table 1. Δ CT values calculated from RT-qPCR of queried miRNAs, miR-10a/b, in HL-60 and MOLT4 cell lines

Sample* Name	Target Name	Δ CT Sample	Δ CT Control**	P-value***
M10a -1	HL-60	3.85	6.300	<0.0001
M10a -2	HL-60	4.08	6.025	
M10a -3	HL-60	4.15	6.165	
M10a -1	MOLT-4	3.36	6.300	0.0008
M10a -2	MOLT-4	4.01	6.025	
M10a -3	MOLT-4	5.31	6.165	
M10b-1	HL-60	4.87	6.37	<0.0001
M10b-2	HL-60	4.55	6.505	
M10b-3	HL-60	4.94	6.195	
M10b-1	MOLT-4	4.37	6.37	0.0042
M10b-2	MOLT-4	5.35	6.505	
M10b-3	MOLT-4	4.86	6.195	

* RT-qPCR has performed for three samples of each cell culture and the numbers indicate corresponding sample.
 ** PBMCs from a normal donor were used as the control for comparing the expressional changes by Δ CT method
 *** P-values < 0.05 are considered meaningful
 SYBR has applied as the reporter. M10a: miRNA-10a; M10b: miRNA-10b

miRNA prediction strategy:

A primary list of miRNAs predicted to be involved in ALL and ALL signaling pathways was generated using the following software tools: Pictar (<http://pictar.mdc-berlin.de/>), microcosm (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/enright-srv/microcosm/htdocs/targets/v5>), Target Scan (<http://www.targetscan.org/> Target Scan release5/2), miRWALK (<http://www.umm.uni-heidelberg.de/apps/zmf/miRwalk>), miRanda (<http://www.microrna.org>), and Diana-microT. Subsequently, enrichment pathway analyses were implemented using the KEGG

(<http://www.genome.jp/kegg/>) and DAVID (<http://david.abcc.ncifcrf.gov/>) databases to establish a network of functionally related genes. A precise literature review across databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus was conducted to identify the most relevant miRNAs targeting the key genes in these pathways.

A ceRNA network was constructed based on the genes obtained and related to the Mir10 family, which were found to be effective in ALL and AML (Figure 1).

Figure 1: ceRNA networks related to Mir family 10 in cancer ALL and AML.

Primer designation

Sense primers with a stem-loop structure were designed for microRNA 10a (RefSeq: NR_029608) and microRNA 10b (RefSeq: NR_029609) using the following tools: AlleleID6,

GeneRunner, oligo6 and mfold which the latter was applied for analysis of the second structures in primers. Additionally, antisense primers, with complementary sequences for the stem part of miRNAs, were designed to facilitate targeting the shorter

miRNAs. Sequences of the specific primers used in this study are provided in the table 2.

Table 3: Resistance rate of *Escherichia coli* To various antibiotics

Homo sapiens microRNA	Sequence (5'-3')	Length (bp)	GC (%)	Tm (°C)
Homo sapiens microRNA 10(a)	AACACGCTACCCTGTAGAACCGAATTTGTGTCGTATCCAGTGCGA ATACCTCGGACCCTGCACTGGATACGAC	73		
MiR-10(a)Forward Primer	AACACGCTACCCTGTAGAACCC	21	52.38	60.31
MiR-10(a)Reverse Primer	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGT	19	57.89	59.68
Homo sapiens microRNA 10(b)	AACACGCTACCCTGTAGAACCGAATTTGTGTCGTATCCAGTGCGA ATACCTCGGACCCTGCACTGGATACGAC	73		
MiR-10(b)Forward Primer	AACACGCTACCCTGTAGAACCC	21	52.38	60.31
MiR-10(b)Reverse Primer	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGT	19	57.89	59.68
RTprimer(specific)	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCACTGGATACGACC ACAAA	50	54	

Statistical analysis

4. Results

Differential expression analyses of miR-10a/b in HL-60 and MOLT-4 cell lines, normalized with the GAPDH gene as the internal control. Mean expression levels of both miR-10a and miR-10b showed a significant increase in both cell lines compared to PBMC cells. Melt curve analysis using the one-way

ANOVA method confirmed that the expression changes are meaningful (P-value < 0.05). Comparison between the expression levels of miR-10a and miR-10b shows that although the changes are close together, overall miR-10a has higher levels. The highest deviation from normal expression belongs to miR-10a with a 3.83-fold change in the MOLT-4 cell line (Figure 2). Graphical data related to melt curves obtained from RT-qPCR reactions for both miRNAs are depicted.

Figure 2. Relative changes in miRNA 10a/b expression levels compared in HL-60 and MOLT-4 cell lines with PBMCs. miRNA expressions were evaluated using RT-qPCR and fold changes calculated as 2^{-ΔΔCT} values normalized with and relative to GAPDH gene as internal control. Asterisks indicate the significance of changes. Figures also demonstrate that miRNA-10a has a more increased expression level than miRNA-10b.

The results of the study showed that out of 104 random samples from children suffering from urinary tract infections, 70.2% of

the samples contained *Escherichia coli* bacteria, which were identified by biochemical characteristics and specific culture.

The prevalence of infection in girls was significantly higher than in boys (78% vs. 22%), which is consistent with the statistically significant p-value of 0.001 ($P < 0.05$), expressing a meaningful relationship between gender and positive urine culture.

Antibiotic sensitivity testing showed that the highest bacterial resistance was to the antibiotic's ampicillin (45%) and methicillin (60%). Also, the extract of *Vaccinium macrocarpon* showed significant antibacterial activity, such that its minimum inhibitory concentration was 50 mg/ml, and increasing the concentration of the extract significantly increased the diameter of the zone of inhibition of bacterial growth. These findings highlight the importance of paying attention to drug resistance and using natural antibacterial agents in the control of urinary tract infections.

5. Discussion

The unexpected role of miR-10 family members was demonstrated when miR-10a was identified as a regulator of ribosome biogenesis, thereby impacting global protein production (12). This involvement of miR-10a in translational regulation of ribosomal proteins (RPs) was uncovered through an unbiased forward analysis of mRNAs interacting with miR-10a. While most validated miRNA targets have been discovered using techniques involving miRNA overexpression or inhibition followed by expression array analyses, or by selecting from lists of predicted targets, these approaches have significant limitations (13,14,15). Many mRNA targets are regulated solely at the level of translational repression without affecting mRNA stability, which often leads to their oversight in expression array-based methods. Bioinformatics predictions of miRNA targets, based mainly on evolutionary conservation of sequence motifs in the 3'-UTR matching miRNA seed regions, have greatly advanced the field by providing testable hypotheses for experimentalists (16,17,18,19). However, these algorithms yield a high rate of false positives and false negatives and rely on relatively small datasets focused either on highly expressed miRNAs or on miRNA overexpression experiments. The expression level of miR-10a influences cellular oncogenic transformation by modulating translational machinery. In cancer, ribosomal protein (RP) expression is deregulated, and specific translation factors promote cellular transformation. Tumor suppressors such as p14ARF, p53, RB, and PTEN negatively regulate ribosome biogenesis, while oncogenes including MYC activate translation-related genes (20,21,22). Mutations in nucleophosmin, observed in acute myeloid leukemia, upregulate miR-10 family members, suggesting miR-10 compensates for defective ribosome biogenesis. MiR-10 regulates RPs' translational stimulation, facilitating cancer transformation without typical oncogenic functions. MiR-10 represents a potential therapeutic target in cancer (31).

In this study, we show that the expressional levels of miR10a/b were increased in two leukemic cell lines, HL-60 and MOLT-4. HL-60 cells as promyelocyte cells are of the most appropriate model systems for research on amylogenesis and AML biology.

It is originally derived from peripheral blood of a 36-year-old female with AML in 1977, and later was classified as M2 by considering the absence of t (15;17) translocation and p53 deletion (10). MOLT-4 is human T-lymphoid cell line derived from a 19-year-old man with ALL (11). To the best of our knowledge, it is the first study that considers both miRNAs in the both leukemic cell lines at the same time which could provide more reliable condition for comparing the results.

While previous reports on AML patients demonstrated rise in mir10a/b levels, the scenario is debating regarding ALL patients in which both decreased and increased levels have been reported (23, 24). Based on the results from this research, overexpression of miR10a/b reaffirms their oncogenic role at least in developing hematopoietic cancers. This idea is in agreement with a recent study by *Thanh Vu et al.* that demonstrated *TP53*, a highly efficient tumor suppressor gene, is regulated by miR-10a and expression of this miRNA in AML patients can be a prognostic biomarker for drug sensitivity (25). We also applied specific databases to extract ceRNA network of gene expression regulating factors related to both mir10a and mir10b. We confirmed that these microRNAs can have critical functions in relation to carcinogenesis and have probably significant co-expression patterns with effective genes as well as oncogenes in several cancers.

Diagnostic criteria of hematological malignancies are indistinct and controversial due to the wide heterogeneity in their clinical and paraclinical presentations. However, owing to the recent advances in genetic methods, custom definitions have been inclining towards molecular pathology and cytogenetic findings (26,27). Genomic approaches by targeting pathobiological mechanisms in different genetic levels, either changes in DNA/RNA sequences or transcriptional/posttranscriptional modifications, have dramatically improved diagnostic, prognostic and therapeutic efficiency in management of these disorders (28,29). In line with this progress, expressional profiling of non-coding RNAs, and in particular microRNAs, in various human tumors may lead to discovery of critical biomarkers and therapeutic targets (30). In this study, we demonstrated that, mir10a and mir10b are the most considerable effective factors in relation to several regulating genes. Thus we express the greatest emphasize on more evaluations to answer the question of whether mir10a and mir10b can be considered as diagnostic and or prognostic factors in leukemia as well as other cancers, and if these factors could be noted for targeted therapy.

Declarations

Ethical Approval

Since no human or animal samples were used in this study, it does not require an ethical approval code.

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